

Internal Communication as a Driver of Organizational Resilience : a systematic literature review using PRISMA method.

Auteur 1 : RHIRHAY Houda,

Auteur 1 : RAFIQ Souad,

RHIRHAY HOUDA Doctorante à l'ENCG Settat,
Laboratoire de Recherche en Transformation et Innovation Managériale
Université Hassan 1er, Maroc

RAFIQ SOUAD : Enseignante Chercheuse à l'ENCG Settat
Laboratoire de Recherche en Transformation et Innovation Managériale
Université Hassan 1er, Maroc.

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Résumé

Au cœur d'un environnement en perpétuelle évolution, dominé par l'incertitude et la complexité (VUCA), la capacité des organisations à anticiper, à se préparer et à s'adapter aux crises constitue un atout stratégique majeur. Parmi les leviers interne susceptibles de soutenir cette résilience, la communication interne occupe une place centrale, en facilitant la coordination, l'engagement et la construction de sens face aux perturbations.

Cet article propose une revue systématique de la littérature visant à clarifier le rôle et les fonctions de la communication interne dans le renforcement de la résilience organisationnelle. Conduite selon le protocole PRISMA, l'étude s'appuie sur la base Scopus et examine les publications récentes durant les cinq dernières années, consacrées à l'articulation entre pratiques communicationnelles et capacité d'adaptation. Cette démarche permet de structurer un champ de recherche encore fragmenté, en identifiant les approches théoriques et méthodologiques les plus significatives.

Au-delà d'une synthèse critique, l'article offre un cadre de référence afin de mieux comprendre les dimensions communicationnelles de la résilience et d'éclairer la conception de stratégies adaptés aux environnements incertains. En soulignant l'importance de considérer la communication interne comme fonction stratégique, ce travail ouvre une perspective pour consolider la préparation organisationnelle et soutenir la continuité dans des contextes de crise ou de changement soudain.

Mots clés : Communication Interne ; Résilience organisationnelle ; Communication de crise ; Sensemaking; Revue systématique ; PRISMA.

Abstract

In an ever-changing environment dominated by uncertainty and complexity (VUCA), the ability of organizations to anticipate, prepare for, and adapt to crises is a major strategic asset. Among the internal levers that can support this resilience, internal communication plays a central role by facilitating coordination, engagement, and meaning-making in the face of disruption.

This article provides a systematic review of the literature aimed at clarifying the role and functions of internal communication in strengthening organizational resilience. Conducted according to the PRISMA protocol, the study draws on the Scopus database and examines recent publications from the last five years devoted to the relationship between communication practices and adaptability. This approach helps to structure a still fragmented field of research by identifying the most significant theoretical and methodological approaches.

Beyond a critical synthesis, the article offers a frame of reference for better understanding the communication dimensions of resilience and informing the design of strategies adapted to uncertain environments. By emphasizing the importance of considering internal communication as a strategic function, this work opens up a perspective for consolidating organizational preparedness and supporting continuity in contexts of crisis or sudden change.

Keywords : Internal communication ;Organizational Resilience ;Crisis communication ;Sensmaking ; Systematic literature review ; PRISMA

Introduction

The current business environment is identified from what is known as the VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) situation and demands the construction of organizational resilience, a critical capability for sustainable development and competitiveness. As a result of global disruptions like COVID-19 crises, changes in geo-politics and technologies, interest in resilience (defined here as the general capability of an organization to “anticipate, prepare for, respond and adapt to incremental change and sudden disruptions in order to survive and prosper (Duchek 2020) has been reinvigorated.

Organizations will have to rely heavily on their internal resources to answer these challenges, where successful internal communication greatly adds value. Internal communication the “strategic management of relationships and interactions between an organization and its employees” (Vercic, Vercic, & Sriramesh, 2012) promotes trust, coordination, sensemaking, and adaptability. Leaders’ communication, especially of top executives, has been proven to have a remarkable impact on employee engagement and trust in crisis (Men, 2015). In addition, there is empirical evidence that employees’ work-role performance is enhanced after crises from the perspective of resilience, where internal crisis communication has played a significant mediating role (Kim, 2020).

Despite simultaneous progress efforts in crisis management and organizational resilience, the two have frequently developed in isolation from one another, and have done so in a siloed fashion (Williams, Gruber, Sutcliffe, Shepherd, & Zhao, 2017). Though the importance of communication is widely acknowledged, a key weakness of scholarship is that it has not published an overall review paper focusing on how internal communication processes contribute to organizational resilience.

This study therefore aims to fill this gap by conducting a systematic literature review that investigates, analyzes and synthesizes the existing research on the relationship between internal communication and organizational resilience. This gap needs to be filled so that scholars and practitioners alike can develop a better-informed understanding of the communicative dimensions of resilience, and a more effective response in building preparation and adaptation towards crises. The research will be in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) to facilitate methodological propriety, transparency and reproducibility (Page et al., 2021; Moher et al., 2009). Systematic review has been familiar as an evidence-based method to structure and aggregate fragmented knowledge

(Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, 2003; Snyder (2019); and to minimize bias by creating stronger bases for the development of theory (Mishra & Mishra, 2023).

This article begins by introducing the topic and contextualizing the growing importance of internal communication in strengthening organizational resilience in a volatile environment. It then outlines the research questions that guide this analysis. The methodological part explains the systematic review process, including the search strategy eligibility criteria and corpus selection conducted in accordance with the PRISMA protocol. The following part presents and analyzes the main results of the review, highlighting both the descriptive trends as well as the thematic insights emerging from recent studies. The discussion then deepens these findings by identifying key theoretical contributions, practical implications and future research opportunities. In conclusion, this article summarizes the main insights and emphasizes the contribution of internal communication as a strategic driver of resilience in organizations.

1. Research questions

To facilitate systematic analysis, the present study has been organized according to the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the functional roles of internal communication to support organizational resilience, in line with empirical and theoretical research?

RQ2: What dimensions of internal communication, (such as leadership communication, crisis communication, communication channels, transparency), are predominantly covered in research on core capabilities of organizational resilience (anticipation, coping, adaptation) ?

2. Methods Search Strategy

2.1 Search Strategy

The conducting of this SR was reporting in accordance with the 2020 PRISMA protocol (Page et al., 2021; Moher et al., 2009). In the search for literature, it was favored to use Scopus as one of the largest and most extended bibliographic databases about management, business and social sciences. The initial query was formulated to directly capture the intersection of the two core constructs of this study (internal communication and organizational resilience). The Boolean equation applied in Scopus was:

TITLE-ABS-KEY("internal communication" AND "organizational resilience")

This formulation was chosen because it targets articles where both concepts appear either in the title, abstract, or author keywords, ensuring a high level of conceptual relevance. At this first

identification stage, no time restriction was applied, in order to retrieve the broadest possible corpus of publications. This resulted in 84 documents.

2.2 Eligibility Criteria

The eligibility criteria were defined to ensure that only relevant and academically rigorous studies were included. Articles were retained if they were peer-reviewed journal papers or systematic reviews, explicitly addressed internal communication as a mechanism or driver within organizational contexts, and demonstrated either an explicit or strong implicit link to organizational resilience, particularly in terms of crisis preparedness, adaptability, business continuity, or organizational learning. Publications in English and French between 2020 and 2025 were considered. Studies focusing solely on individual or family resilience (e.g., children, psychology, or education), articles dealing with external or marketing communication (such as public relations or branding), and non-academic material (conference abstracts, reports, book chapters, or editorials) were excluded. The selection process followed PRISMA's four stages. In the identification phase, the initial Scopus query "internal communication" AND "organizational resilience" produced 84 records with no time restriction. During screening, a temporal filter (2020–2025) was applied to capture the period where organizational resilience became central, particularly in the context of COVID-19, reducing the sample to 66 documents. Restricting results to journal articles only yielded 53 records. In the eligibility phase, subject areas were narrowed to Business, Management and Accounting, Economics, Econometrics and Finance, and Social Sciences, which produced 35 articles. Abstracts were carefully reviewed, and studies classified under Business/Management but focused exclusively on financial or technical resilience without reference to communication were excluded. Finally, at the inclusion stage, 20 articles were retained for systematic analysis. These studies explicitly addressed internal communication as a factor influencing organizational resilience, covering themes such as internal crisis communication, leadership transparency, employee engagement, and knowledge sharing.

2.3 Justification of Final Corpus

Although 35 articles initially met the subject-area criteria, only 20 were kept after close eligibility assessment. The main reason for exclusion at this stage was that many "Business and Management" papers referred to resilience in a technical, economic, or purely structural sense, without discussing the role of internal communication. To maintain conceptual precision and coherence with the research objective, only the studies linking communication practices to resilience outcomes were included.

2.3 PRISMA Flow Diagram

Figure 1: PRISMA Flowchart

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

A descriptive analysis of our corpus (20 articles) highlights interesting trends on how the interrelation between internal communication and organizational resilience has been adopted by researchers. The most salient to us is the huge jump in academic interest that revealed itself after COVID-19, instigating a global disruption which, it seems, has raised scholars' awareness to how pivotal communication can be in terms of building organizational resilience.

Temporal Distribution of Publications

Examining the "Documents by year" chart, there is a huge peak in 2025 where 8 documents were published contributing to 40% of our corpus. This is some exponential growth from all the way back (2 articles in 2021, 1 in 2022, 3 in 2023 and then 6 in 2024.) Evidently, recent global turmoil has provoked academic curiosity around the communication mechanisms that support those organizations strong enough not only to have survived but also to have thrived in tumultuous times. For the 2024-2025 interval it covers, it is 70% of all publications, suggesting that this not only is a topic of current examination but also that interest in this area of work has significantly increased.

Geographic Distribution of Studies

The geographical analysis, presented in the chart "Documents by country or territory", shows rich and diverse national contexts, including a significant bias for developed economies. UK and US are the most prolific countries with 4 and 3 publications, respectively, Netherlands, and Egypt with 2 publications each. The rest of the corpus covers 11 countries, such as Sweden, Australia, Brazil and Hong Kong but also rarely studied contexts such as Palestine, Ukraine and Pakistan. While unevenly distributed, this geographic diversity has added richness to the collection by including a broad range of cultural and economic perspectives from mature market economies to political unstable or conflict affected settings.

Diversity of Sectoral Applications

What’s also so revealing is that the 20 articles cover such a wide variety of industries which underlines just how universal internal communication is for driving organisational resilience. Healthcare (hospitals, care homes), banking and finance; higher education (universities) and tourism & leisure are the top industries. Other sectors such as critical infrastructure, technology (IT), and even sports organizations aren’t far behind. This diversity highlights that although the precise problems may differ, the importance of effective internal communication in building resilience is a concern common to all types of organizations .

Table 1: Overview of the 20 Selected Articles

Authors	Year	Title	Journal	Country	Sector	Citations
Ivanovic, N., de Vries, T.A., van der Vegt, G.S., Van Donk, D.P.	2025	Handling Disruption Concurrence: The Importance of Inter- and Intra- Departmental Communication for Critical Infrastructure Resilience	Journal of Supply Chain Management	Netherlands	Critical Infrastructure	0
Hong, H.J., Botwina, G.	2025	Postponed Olympic Dreams: High-Performance Athletes' Experience in Coping with Postponed Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games	Physical Culture and Sport, Studies and Research	UK/Poland	Sports	0
Korobkina, T., Dashenkova, N.	2025	Culture of Dignity as the Foundation of Organizational Culture of Humanistic Management. Modern Research in the IT Industry	Technology Audit and Production Reserves	Ukraine	Technology	0

Authors	Year	Title	Journal	Country	Sector	Citations
Eriksson, K.M., Lycke, L.	2025	May the force of lifelong learning be with you – sustainable organizational learning in HEIs meeting competence needs in industry	Learning Organization	Sweden	Higher Education	9
Mutlu, H., Baykara Mat, S.T.	2025	Accreditation through the eyes of nurse managers: an infinite staircase or a phenomenon that evaporates like water	Journal of Health Organization and Management	Turkey	Healthcare	0
Tanbour, K.M., Ben Saada, M., Nour, A.I.	2025	The impact of implementing an internal control system on banking risk management during crises: a case study on banks operating in Palestine	International Journal of Disclosure and Governance	Palestine/Tunisia	Banking	0
Tachkova, E.R., Brannon, G.E.	2025	Psychological resilience and crisis READINESS: connecting employee well-being and internal crisis communication	Journal of Communication Management	Hong Kong/USA	General	0

Authors	Year	Title	Journal	Country	Sector	Citations
Adamu, A.A., Raza, S.H., Mohamad, B.B.	2024	Organizational resilience: unveiling the role of strategic internal crisis management on employee sensemaking and sensegiving	International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management	Malaysia/Pakistan	General	6
Gao, X., Jaggi, J., Yan, H.	2024	Internal auditors and crisis management: a post-crisis outcome evaluation	Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change	USA	Higher Education	0
Langi Sasongko, P.K.B., Janssen, M., De Bruijne, M.C.	2024	Building towards organisational resilience and complexity leadership: A case study of impacts and changes in a Dutch blood establishment during COVID-19	BMJ Leader	Netherlands	Healthcare	0
Shertzer, Y.	2024	HR under fire The role of HR in war time	Human Resources Management and Services	Israel	General	1
Sánchez, M.A., de Batista, M.	2023	Business continuity for times of vulnerability: Empirical evidence	Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management	Argentina	General	17

Authors	Year	Title	Journal	Country	Sector	Citations
Liu-Lastres, B., Wen, H., Okumus, F.	2023	Examining employees' affective and behavioral responses to internal crisis communication in times of COVID-19	International Journal of Hospitality Management	USA	Hospitality	12
Elshaer, I.A., Saad, S.K.	2022	Entrepreneurial resilience and business continuity in the tourism and hospitality industry: the role of adaptive performance and institutional orientation	Tourism Review	Saudi Arabia/Egypt	Tourism	44
Al Balushi, M.	2021	How internal transparency impacts organizational resilience	International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management	UK	Public Sector	13
Contreras García, F., Alvarado, T.E.G.	2021	Business Resilience and Social Inclusion: A Critical Reflection on Internal Marketing	Mercados y Negocios	Mexico	General	4
Yeomans, L., Roberts-Bowman, S.	2021	Internal crisis communication and the social construction of emotion: university leaders' sensegiving discourse during the COVID-19 pandemic	Journal of Communication Management	UK	Higher Education	29

3.2 Thematic Synthesis

Our thematic analysis of the 20 articles identified five interrelating themes that explain how internal communication is a foundation for organizational resilience. These themes (1) crisis communication and sensemaking, (2) HR and leadership engagement, (3) learning and agility, (4) crisis management and continuity, and (5) sector-specific applications don't exist in isolation but rather weave together to create a rich tapestry of understanding about how organizations can communicate their way through adversity.

Theme 1: Crisis Communication & Sensemaking

This theme emerges as perhaps the most fundamental, exploring how internal communication during crises helps employees make sense of ambiguous and threatening events while building shared understanding that guides collective action. The work of Yeomans and Roberts-Bowman (2021) provides particularly compelling insights here. Their analysis of university leaders' discourse during the COVID-19 pandemic reveals how narratives of organizational competence, empathy, and community contribute to the social construction of emotions and help reduce employee cognitive dissonance. It's fascinating how they show that effective crisis communication isn't just about information transfer it's about emotional regulation and meaning-making.

Similarly, Adamu et al. (2024) show that strategy communication during the internal crisis promotes employee sensemaking and giving, which further improves engagement and organizational resilience. What's striking, too, is how they demonstrate that employees don't merely sit still for crisis messages but instead actively interpret the message and then repeat it to others throughout the organization.

Tachkova and Brannon (2025) take this further by proposing a theoretical framework that connects internal crisis communication to employee well-being and psychological crisis readiness. Their work highlights something we often overlook: that managing emotions and stress isn't just about individual well-being it's a strategic imperative for organizational resilience. In this regard, coping with uncertainty requires not only structural preparedness but also psychological resilience, as emotional regulation and adaptability play a decisive role in sustaining motivation and performance during crises (Hong & Botwina, 2025).

Theme 2: HR & Leadership Engagement

The role of leadership and human resources function emerges as another critical theme, with leaders' communication setting the tone for crisis response and directly influencing employee trust and engagement. Shertzer's (2024) examination of HR's role during wartime provides a

stark but illuminating example. The study highlights functions like uncertainty reduction, morale maintenance, and internal tension management roles that become even more critical when organizations face existential threats.

What impresses most in the work of Eriksson et al (2024) at HE institutions is they call for joint commitment across all organisational aspects, tightly knitted with strong leadership to surpass bureaucracy and stimulate organisational learning. Their idea of creating a “chain-of-trust” within the organization compliments ours in so much as communication acts as the social glue, that connects different entities and structures, holding them intact during stressful moments.

Mutlu and Baykara Mat's (2025) examination of employee vs. patient-focused approaches to healthcare demonstrates that positive team dynamics such as collaboration and empathy strengthens service quality and employee satisfaction, both important components of health system resilience. Their work is a reminder that in fields that revolve around people, internal communication is not simply about operational efficiency; it's about keeping up the kinds of human connections that make care possible.

Theme 3: Learning & Agility

Structures success is organizational learning and agility, which will allow organizations to change and become superior in face of disruptions. Eriksson and Lycke (2025) report on the role of industry-academia collaboration in which organizational learning, facilitated by open communication and cross-functional knowledge transfer, can help develop more agile and sustainable educational organization. What their work shows is something deep: that learning isn't some academic skill, but a social activity and being encouraged to learn in a certain way was clearly part of how they became so good at it.

Korobkina and Dashenkova's (2025) work in the IT sector proposes a dignity-based organizational culture model where ethical communication and reflective practices foster psychological resilience and team agility in turbulent work environments. Their approach is particularly relevant in our current era of rapid technological change and digital burnout.

Theme 4: Crisis Management & Continuity

This theme focuses on how internal communication supports crisis management processes and business continuity. Sánchez & de Batista (2023) also discover that collaborative work and efficient communication with stakeholders are strategic to facing disruption among firms operating in very volatile macroeconomic scenarios. Their study, set in the fragile economic conditions of Argentina, offers a rare example in which communication can act as an anchor when it feels like everything else is upended.

Elshaer and Saad's (2022) work shows that entrepreneurial resilience in tourism and hospitality is mediated by adaptive performance and institutional orientation both factors heavily influenced by communication quality and networks. Their findings suggest that resilience isn't just about individual characteristics but about how well entrepreneurs can communicate and connect with their broader ecosystem.

Tanbour et al. s (2025) study on the effect of internal control systems on bank risk management in time of crisis reveals that strong ICTS leads to improved risk management efficiency. This is a reminder that in heavily regulated industries, communication is not just about relationships it's about compliance, risk management and operational integrity.

Theme 5: Sector-Specific Applications

Finally, our analysis reveals that while the basic principles of internal communication for resilience are universal, their application varies significantly across sectors. In healthcare, communication is essential for ensuring patient safety and care quality during crises (Mutlu & Baykara Mat, 2025). In critical infrastructure, highly inter- and intra-departmental communication is required to respond to simultaneous outages (Ivanovic et al., 2025). In hospitality, internal crisis communication affects employee psychological safety and turnover intentions (Liu-Lastres et al., 2023).

By focusing on these sector-specific studies, they can offer useful guideposts when designing one's own communication strategy within an industry, a reminder that it is not "one-size fits all" in terms of crisis communication.

3. Discussion

This systematic literature review has illuminated the multifaceted role of internal communication as a driver of organizational resilience. Our analysis of 20 carefully selected articles reveals a field of research that's not just growing rapidly particularly since 2020 but also converging around key themes that help us understand how organizations can better anticipate, manage, and adapt to crises. What emerges is a picture of internal communication not as a simple information conduit, but as a strategic process of meaning-making, engagement, and learning that sits at the very heart of organizational resilience. Effective internal communication between audit teams and management enhances the organization's ability to detect risks early, coordinate corrective actions, and sustain resilience during periods of financial or operational uncertainty (Wahyuandari, Minarni, & Hariyani, 2025).

4.1 Synthesis of key findings

One of our most significant findings is that internal communication serves multiple interconnected functions in building resilience. It's not just about getting information from point A to point B it's about creating shared understanding, managing emotions, building trust, and facilitating learning. The theme of crisis communication and sensemaking emerged as particularly central, highlighting how leaders' ability to frame events, manage emotions, and construct coherent narratives is fundamental to maintaining organizational cohesion and employee mobilization during uncertain times (Yeomans & Roberts-Bowman, 2021; Adamu et al., 2024). What's particularly fascinating is how this "sensegiving" function transforms anxiety and confusion into shared understanding and coordinated action. It's almost like internal communication serves as the organization's nervous system, helping it process and respond to environmental stimuli in a coordinated way. The second major insight concerns the critical importance of leadership and HR engagement. Our analysis shows that leader visibility, empathy, and transparency are determining factors in employee trust (Shertzer, 2024). The HR function plays a pivotal role in establishing support systems, managing talent during crises, and promoting a culture of well-being (Mutlu & Baykara Mat, 2025). The alignment between leadership discourse and HR actions emerges as crucial for reinforcing organizational credibility and member engagement. Third, we found a strong connection between internal communication, organizational learning, and agility. Open and transparent communication fosters a culture where mistakes are seen as learning opportunities and knowledge flows freely across organizational silos (Eriksson & Lycke, 2025). This collective learning capacity forms the foundation of organizational agility the ability to adapt quickly and effectively to changing circumstances. Finally, our review confirms that internal communication is an essential component of crisis management and business continuity. Robust information and communication systems enable better risk assessment, more effective response coordination, and greater ability to maintain critical operations during disruption (Tanbour et al., 2025; Sánchez & de Batista, 2023).

4.2 Theoretical contributions

This systematic review contributes to the literature on organizational resilience and internal communication in several important ways. First, it offers an integrated synthesis of what has been a fragmented research corpus, identifying key themes and clarifying conceptual links between them. In response to RQ1, it demonstrates that the functional roles of internal communication extend far beyond simple information transmission, encompassing psychologic

al functions (sensemaking, emotion management), social functions (cohesion, trust), and strategic functions (learning, adaptation).

Second, in response to RQ2, our review identifies the dimensions of internal communication most studied in relation to resilience. Crisis communication, leadership communication, and transparency clearly emerge as predominant dimensions. However, the review also highlights emerging dimensions such as ethical communication (Korobkina & Dashenkova, 2025) and cross-functional communication (Eriksson & Lycke, 2025) that deserve greater attention from researchers.

Third, this review supports the idea that organizational resilience isn't just about material or financial resources, but also about social and communicative capabilities. It reinforces capability-based approaches to resilience (Duchek, 2020) by positioning internal communication as a meta-capability that enables the development of other resilience capabilities such as anticipation, crisis management, and adaptation.

4.3 Practical implications

Our findings have significant practical implications for leaders and communication professionals. First, they underscore the need to invest in internal communication not as a support function, but as a strategic function essential to organizational survival and prosperity. This means equipping internal communication teams with the resources and skills necessary to play a strategic advisory role with senior management.

Second, leaders must develop their crisis communication competencies, particularly their ability to demonstrate empathy, communicate transparently, and construct narratives that give meaning to employee experiences. Leadership that embraces complexity and adaptive coordination has been shown to strengthen organizational resilience in high-pressure environments (Langi Sasongko, Janssen, & De Bruijne, 2024). Leadership development should include modules on crisis communication and emotion management skills that are often overlooked in traditional management training.

Third, organizations should establish systems and processes that foster open communication, cross-functional dialogue, and continuous learning. Implementing internal transparency practices enhances communication between employees and management, fostering mutual trust and reinforcing the foundations of organizational resilience (Al Balushi, 2021). This might include collaborative communication platforms, post-crisis debriefings, and regular feedback mechanisms that keep the organizational conversation flowing even during calm periods.

Finally, it's important to adapt internal communication strategies to the specificities of each sector and organizational culture. The sector-specific examples in our review can serve as starting points for developing tailored approaches that recognize the unique challenges and opportunities in different contexts.

4.4 Limitations and future research directions

Despite its contributions, our review has several limitations that point toward future research opportunities. Our search was limited to the Scopus database, and while comprehensive, it's possible that relevant articles published in other databases or non-indexed journals were missed. Additionally, our focus on English and French language publications may introduce linguistic bias, potentially missing important insights from other linguistic traditions.

The retrospective nature of literature reviews also means we can't capture the most recent developments in real-time. Given how rapidly this field is evolving, particularly in response to ongoing global disruptions, there's a constant need for updated syntheses.

These limitations open several avenues for future research. Comparative studies across different sectors would help us better understand how sectoral context influences the relationship between internal communication and resilience. Longitudinal research would allow us to track the evolution of communication strategies and their effects on resilience over time. It would also be valuable to explore more deeply the role of new communication technologies social media platforms, artificial intelligence, virtual reality in strengthening organizational resilience. Finally, most studies focus on large organizations; additional research on SMEs and startups would be useful for understanding their specific challenges and practices in communication and resilience. The entrepreneurial context, with its resource constraints and informal structures, likely presents unique opportunities and challenges for building resilience through communication.

Conclusion

This systematic literature review has provided comprehensive answers to our initial research questions, clarifying the functional roles and key dimensions of internal communication that support organizational resilience. What emerges is a picture of internal communication as far more than a simple information channel it's a strategic lever that enables organizations to navigate the complexity and uncertainty of our contemporary world.

In response to RQ1, we identified several functional roles of internal communication: a psychological role in sensemaking and emotion management, a social role in building trust and cohesion, and a strategic role in facilitating learning and adaptation. These roles are interdependent and contribute synergistically to the organization's overall resilience capacity.

In response to RQ2, we found that crisis communication, leadership communication, and transparency are the most studied dimensions. However, emerging dimensions such as ethical communication and cross-functional communication are gaining importance, suggesting an evolution toward a more holistic understanding of internal communication.

Theoretically, this review reinforces capability-based approaches to resilience by positioning internal communication as a fundamental meta-capability. It calls for greater integration between communication theories, leadership theories, and crisis management theories to develop more robust models of organizational resilience.

Practically, our findings underscore the need for organizations to invest in internal communication as a strategic function. Leaders and managers must be trained to communicate effectively during crises, and organizations must cultivate a culture of open, transparent, and learning-oriented communication. Communication strategies must be adapted to specific sectoral and cultural contexts to be fully effective.

As organizations continue to face unprecedented disruptions from global pandemics to geopolitical tensions to climate change the ability to communicate effectively internally has never been more crucial. Internal communication isn't a luxury; it's a necessity for long-term survival and prosperity. By fostering meaning, trust, and agility, it constitutes the true beating heart of the resilient organization. Communication that encourages knowledge exchange and motivation among employees not only strengthens social inclusion but also enhances organizational resilience by fostering trust, collaboration, and continuous learning (Contreras García & González Alvarado, 2021). Future research must continue to explore this dynamic domain, particularly examining the impact of new technologies and the specific challenges of different organizational types, to provide practitioners with the knowledge they need to build

stronger, more resilient organizations for the future. The conversation about internal communication and resilience is far from over in many ways, it's just beginning.

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